

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D6.4 — FAIR assistance

WP6 – FAIRification and Provenance Services
Lead Beneficiary: UOXF
WP leader: Isabelle Perseil (INSERM) and Petr Holub (BBMRI)
Contributing partner(s): UOXF, UMAS, and LUMC
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Authors of this deliverable: **Susanna-Assunta Sansone, Allyson Lister, Milo Thurston, Philippe Rocca-Serra, Dominique Batista, Ramon Granell, Prakhyat Gailani, Michel Dumontier.**

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Executive Summary

The research infrastructures that participate in EOSC-Life use FAIRsharing¹ as the project's registry for data resources and standards. The FAIRsharing registry ensures that both data and standards are richly described, interrelated (e.g. which standards are implemented by a particular database) and visualised, as well as being Findable (e.g. discoverable and citable via a DOI), Accessible (e.g. with a clearly described method of content access), Interoperable (e.g. it is clear which standards are implemented by different databases and how they are related) and Re-usable (e.g. explicit terms of use of the data are provided to users). This ensures that the 2041 databases and 1641 standards currently (July 2023) in the FAIRsharing registry are indeed FAIR. Nevertheless, the size and complexity of the FAIRsharing registry makes navigation difficult for first time users. This deliverable summarises the work of WP6 to create the FAIRsharing Assistant², a wizard that guides stakeholders so that they can discover, learn about and use the FAIRsharing registry. The FAIRsharing Assistant leverages the rich description of standards and database and guides the users to filter and select the relevant records according to their subject area(s), data types and needs. The FAIRsharing Assistant is complemented by two components: the new FAIRsharing Educational page³, with infographics and factsheets covering content and functionalities for all users, and the FAIRassist page⁴, which lists existing tools developed by the community to assess and evaluate FAIRness. The FAIR Assistant is a DEM deliverable, and this report accompanies it to provide summary and background information.

Project Objectives

This deliverable has contributed directly to the following WP6 and WP1 objectives:

- a. Develop guidance to help RIs to follow and implement the FAIR Principles (WP6).
- b. Advance the evolution of RI repository infrastructure for EOSC (WP1)
- c. Implement of FAIR services and WP1 standards for RI data/data resources (WP1)

¹ <https://fairsharing.org/>

² <https://assist.fairsharing.org/>

³ <https://fairsharing.org/educational>

⁴ <https://fairassist.org/>

Report on the Deliverable

The **FAIRsharing Assistant** (beta)⁵ wizard consists of a Javascript (Vue.js) client powered by data stored in the FAIRsharing database (PostgreSQL and Elasticsearch). The data are accessed by means of the FAIRsharing API⁶, for which new search filters specific to the assistant have been developed. The FAIRsharing Assistant source code⁷ is available under the GNU AGPL v. 3.0. Both the FAIRsharing Assistant and API are hosted on hardware at the University of Oxford, a member of the ELIXIR-UK Node. FAIRsharing is delivered to the ELIXIR, the EOSC-Life and the broad community as a resource of the ELIXIR-UK Node's service delivery plan. Figure 1 shows a snippet of the decision tree and how users are guided to select and filter on characteristics of databases and/or standards, relevant to their subject area(s), data types and needs.

Figure 1

The **FAIRsharing Educational** page provides users with infographics and factsheets, covering content and functionalities for all stakeholders. This has been co-developed by the UOXF team and the FAIRsharing Community Champions^{8,9}. The latter initiative was launched with seed funds from RDA and EOSC Future, as part of the Domain Ambassador Programme^{10,11}, and includes an EOSC-life representative. Figure 2 shows the material that has been released and the one in preparation, as well as an example for researchers. In addition to “FAIRsharing in a nutshell” the rest of the educational material is organised in categories: FAIRsharing content (on standards, databases, policies, as well as Collections), FAIRsharing for you (specific to stakeholders),

⁵ <https://assist.fairsharing.org>

⁶ <https://fairsharing.org/licence>

⁷ <https://github.com/FAIRsharing/FAIRsharing-Assistant>

⁸ <https://blog.fairsharing.org/?p=567>

⁹ https://fairsharing.org/community_champions

¹⁰ <https://blog.fairsharing.org/?p=501>

¹¹ <https://eoscfuture-grants.eu/node/262>

FAIRsharing functionalities (on key features the registry offers), FAIRsharing behind the scenes (e.g., on how the registry is FAIR in itself, how the content is curated).

Figure 2

The **FAIRassist** page indicates existing tools developed by the community to assess and evaluate FAIRness. As of July 2023, there are 25 tools registered. These encompass both manual questionnaires, checklists and automated tests that help users understand how to achieve a state of "FAIRness", and how this can be measured and improved. The FAIRsharing team is working closely with the EOSC FAIR Metrics and Data Quality Task Force, which SA Sansone is a member of, and as result FAIRsharing and its content has become a core element of the FAIR assessment and FAIR assistance¹².

The deliverable utilises input from the WP6 Task 6.1 on FAIR-related user personas (archetypes) and developed a decision tree for the initial FAIR guidance based on FAIRsharing content. Additional work on both the FAIRsharing Assistant and FAIRsharing Educational will be done to further implement the Task 6.1 personas, beyond the end of EOSC-Life, since FAIRsharing is embedded in ELIXIR as well as newly funded EOSC projects, and the work will be carried out with and for domain experts, stakeholders and the FAIRsharing Community Champions.

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed: No

¹² https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2023-01/Report%20on%20the%20FAIR%20Evaluation%20events_final_sub.pdf

Adjustments

As detailed in the 2nd project amendment, rather than a software to provide personalised FAIR guidance, the deliverable has produced three components: the FAIRassist page, the FAIRsharing Educational page and the FAIRsharing Assistant wizard.

